

A Study to Identify the Psychological Problems of Students at Primary Level

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Abstract

The main objective of this research paper is to acquire an understanding of psychological problems among students, particularly within the academic learning and achievement of academic goals. The research population contains all the primary schools of District of Rawalpindi. Twenty primary schools were selected as sample of the study. Moreover 20 teachers, 20 parents and 40 students selected from each primary school. The study objectives were 1) To identify the psychological problems to students on primary level.

Key Words

Psychological
Problems, Academic,
Learning Disabilities

2) To study and examine why these psychological problems emerged and how to take precautionary steps to reduce them. The Interviews were as a research instrument. Data was collected and analysis revealed the following conclusion: The major causes of psychological problems among students were academic problems, learning disabilities, and exam stress. It is also recommended that newly hired teachers be trained in child psychology before they have the responsibility to teach children.

Introduction

The underdeveloped society and the people of this country belong to Muslim Ummah. As a Muslim each should strive to know the problems in teaching and learning field in the schools. Acquiring education is the basic responsibility of a Muslim. In the early days of Islam education was given special attention. Today too it is the education that is given a reasonable portion of annual Budget. Through after approval of 18th Constitutional amendment, education is related to provinces yet federal government spends considerable portion of Budget on education in the province as well. The District does not have the asset to promote such department whose expenditure is less than its profit. But the bitter facts are before us that the education department as a whole and its sub units are on a constant regression instead of so many expenditures and funds allocation to the education. The education system in the country is on a constant degradation without a small stop for the lost forty years. Each government military or political with renewed efforts and allocation of considerable fund the result is zero. This flood of degradation in education cannot be stopped unless we establish our education structure on scientific and psychological foundation (Ahmad, et al. 2007).

In present time each field needs psychological solutions. Psychology prevails in every field of life particularly in the field of education, Industry, law, investigation, medical, advertising, propaganda etc. Revolutionary changes have been formatted after introducing psychological principles in social perplexities. In hospital patients are treated in accordance with the psychological rules. The doctors and other staff of hospital behave the patients according to rules set by the psychological experts. It is used to establish good relation between the workers and industrialist. So it is that we see psychology in each field of life. It is also time for us to apply psychological principles in the education as well.

Psychological problems are an integral part of a person 's life. Individuals typically encounter psychological difficulties in their jobs, maintaining relationships, health issues, and feeling stressed by factors such as workload, inability to get enough sleep, diet, etc. When psychological problems that individuals encounter impact them to a large degree, then it is important that they try remedies. The different kinds of psychological issues that individuals experience are depression, stress and anxiety. Students do experience psychological issues in educational institutions at all levels (Mathew, 2017).

The life of a student is subjected to different aspects which cause psychological problems. The main ones include pressure from educators with the expectation to excel, and uncertain future and

difficulties, expected for incorporation into the program, learning challenges, difficulties in understanding academic concepts, financial issues, health issues, exam stress, and witnessing discriminatory treatment or some sort of violent and criminal actions within educational institutions (Jellinek, et al.1999)

Students' abilities vary as regards coping with psychological issues. Students' psychological problems are also influenced by social, physical, emotional, and family issues that affect their ability to learn and academic performance (Mathew, 2017). Some of the students find it hard to manage psychological issues and suffer setbacks. Whereas others take it as opportunities and are persistent in their work. Typically, in the process of achieving desired academic goals, when students encounter psychological difficulties and believe that they are becoming impediments, they seek solutions from professional counselors.

Psychological problems can cause physical as well as mental health disruptions. Students' main factors that would lead to removing impediments that occur in achieving desired objectives and goals are finding successful approaches to different forms of psychological issues. Causing a decrease in psychological issues and following a healthy lifestyle are important factors in achieving academic goals and having good academic results.

Adolescence reflects the time of transition between childhood and adulthood, during which a person undergoes a number of biological and emotional transformations. Hall denoted this time as "storm and tension" and notes that "conflict is natural at this stage of development" (Hall, G.1903). Throughout this period, adolescents suffer from various forms of problems / dysfunctions and conflicts that ultimately impair normal psychosocial development which aggravates psychosocial dysfunction.

In many ways, researchers have been trying to determine psycho-social dysfunction. However, an understanding of psychosocial dysfunction concludes that it is synonymous with conditions that internalize and externalize, respectively. Depression and anxiety (internalization of diseases) and delinquency, aggression and difficulties in education and truancy (outsourcing disorders) are the most common disorders. Mostly adolescence affected by the atmosphere of home and education. Schools play a key role in a young person's life, as they spend a great deal of time in school, doing extracurricular activities and doing scholastic work at home. School is an institute, critical to the personality development of adolescents, that contributes to the overall educational and socializing procedures (Ahmad, et al. 2007)

In a major phase of socialization, the lack of care for children's mental wellbeing and adolescence could lead to life-long mental health effects and lower societal capacities (Polaha, Dalton and Allen 2011). More specifically, a proper psycho-social growth of adolescents with a good academic level, physical health and adequate financial, mental, and psychological wellbeing is reflected. (WHO 2001)

Statement of the Problem

The aim of this research work was to find out the Psychological Problems of Students at School in Primary Level. There are a number of causes of psychological problems among such as problems in understanding academic concepts, exam stress, undesirable academic outcome, financial problems, health problems, stress and Work Pressure.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to identify all the problems that occurred in school to the students on primary level. It is important to inform that these youngest citizens are the country's future. If they experience these problems that cannot be solved in the nib at the most basic stage, so they can never be curbed in the future and that will be passed from generation to generation without seeking any solution to it, so it was thought that such issues should not only be recognized but suggested solutions so that future generations can be saved from these psychological problems.

Following are the objectives of the study were:

1. To identify the psychological problems to students on primary level.
2. To study and examine why these psychological problems emerged and how to take precautionary steps to reduce them.

Research Questions

For this purpose, the following research questions have been asked for answers;

1. What are the psychological problems to students on primary level?
2. What are the causes of psychological problems to students on primary level?

Significance of the Study

Keeping in mind the originality of the subject, it is recommended that in this period of uncertainty when everything is wrapped in dark and black cloth and there appears to be no beam of light from outside except our own efforts, we, the people of Pakistan and, in particular, the teaching staff in school, should be made aware of all the upcoming educational problems. That if these were not fixed timely this would deteriorate not a small community but the entire District that would never even be compensated for by collective effort. There are few key focus points that will be helpful; Which are Put in all common efforts with full strength to avoid these problems.

1. To face the problem bravely and courageously
2. To investigate the matters and problem carefully without any bias to any part of the community or the caste.
3. To train the young at the very small level so as to make them feel responsible for the problems.
4. To put the things in the deaf ears of the government authorities that as the things are rapidly changing that demands rapid solution and rapid measures to be taken against the unfavorable change as to ensure the safety of the nation at large.
5. After going through these papers, it may be expected that proper measure be taken against the ill will in the schools on primary level and the situation may be safeguarded from deterioration.
6. In the schools where the teachers are doing their jobs well keeping in view the psychological aspects in the studies may be awarded.
7. To ensure that new lot of teachers may be trained on the educational psychology as well.

Delimitation of the Study

The topic requires a very comprehensive study, but due to a shortage of available resources, it was decided to keep me to the school that is easily accessible and accessible. Both the old and retired school staff was consulted to better examine the issues and they also shared rich ideas with me. This research work was delimited to the twenty (20) primary school students, teachers, and parents.

Material and Methods

Research Design

In order to properly investigate the project, twenty (20) schools in the local area have been selected and their staff, students and parents have been targeted for interviews. No questionnaire was communicated to any teacher, influential parent or student in order to have direct contact with the community and the teaching staff. The following methodology has been adopted:

Research Methodology

This section of research design explains analysis for the thesis and the various components used in the design.

Nature of the Study

The study is entirely descriptive. Interviews were prepared to learn the perception of psychological problems of students and teachers.

Population

The research population contains all the primary schools of District of Rawalpindi.

Sample

Twenty primary schools were selected as sample of the study. Moreover 20 teachers, 20 parents and 40 students selected from each primary school.

Tool for Collection of Data

Data collected through interviews with three groups, teachers, parents and students.

Interviews of Teachers

In almost all areas, 20 teachers from different schools were selected and contacted for timely interviews in accordance with questionnaires on psychological problems for school students.

Interviews of Students

In all 20 schools in the area, 40 students from different classes who were able to analyze problems and situations were asked about the prevailing situation in their schools.

Interviews of Parents

A survey of the project was conducted by 20 parents of primary school children in the same schools. Although they did not know the psychological problems of the students, their reactions indicated that they practice the same behavior with their children to make them feel free and easy.

Results

The collected data was presented in tabular form by applying descriptive statistics such as frequency score; mean score, standard deviation, percentage and t-value for data analysis. Detailed descriptions of the results were presented in the following tables;

Analysis Table of Interview from Teachers

Table 1. There are (20) Twenty Teachers were Interviewed and their Response to the Questionnaire is as Under.

S. No	Question Description	Yes	Neutral	No	Total	%age
1	They know a lot about psychology	15	0	5	20	100
2.	Is there a psychological problem for students in their schools?	1	1	18	20	100
3	Motivate students to	18	1	1	20	100
4	Students are often late	2	0	18	20	100
5	The students are punished for coming late	2	0	18	20	100
6	Students who are intentionally absent from school	2	3	15	20	100
7.	There is a long absence of students	2	0	18	20	100
8.	Students do their homework	20	0	0	20	100
9	Students are acting rudely	2	0	18	20	100
10	Parents often go to school to monitor their children.	8	4	8	20	100
11	Parent or community complaint	2	0	18	20	100

A total number of 20 teachers were selected for interview after ensuring their availability. The teachers responded in favor of familiarization with psychology is 15 out of 20 while 18 out of 20 in report of psychological problems to students, motivation of student is in favor of 18 out of 20, majority students are not late in time to school. No student intentionally ever absents from school, 100 % of students do their homework before they come to school; students' fine behavior is 100%. Only 44% of parents visit the school to monitor their kids' regularity to school. This aspect needs and the %age should be high. No complaint against students or society. This situation in school is very exemplary.

Analysis Table of Parent's Interview

Table 2. 20 Parents Particularly Mothers were Interviewed in Accordance to the Questionnaire

S. No	Question Description	Yes	Neutral	No	Total	%age
1	They know the name of the teachers at school in their area	11	0	9	20	100
2.	The teachers arrive at the school on time	9	11	0	20	100
3	Education starts in time	20	0	0	20	100
4	Teachers beat schoolchildren	0	0	20	20	100
5	Girls complain about the teachers	0	0	20	20	100
6	The teachers hold parental meetings	3	16	2	21	100
7.	Children do homework	20	0	0	20	100
8.	The students feel satisfied with learning	20	0	0	20	100
9	Their children are disrespectful to teachers	0	0	20	20	100
10	They allowed their children to use mobiles	0	0	20	20	100
11	Children dodge them	5	7	8	20	100
12	Children have some emotional disorder	0	0	20	20	100

The parents' interviews were also interesting but space and time limitations force us to abreast to the project study. Only 56% of community know the name of teachers, 47% community is satisfactory of the regularity of teachers to schools, 100% of the community is satisfied with schools in time start. 100% of the community believes of no physical punishment in school. No student at home shows allergy to the teacher's behavior. 15% of the teachers conducting meetings, 100% of students do their homework and 100 % of students are satisfied with teaching methodology. The behavior of the student to teachers is 100% fine according to their parents. 100% of parents are against use of mobile phone by their kids. 27% of kids sometimes dodge their parents and they arouse no psychological problem to the students so far.

Analysis Table of Interview from Students

Table 3. There are 40 Students of Different Classes were Interviewed and were Inquired According to the Questionnaire as Under: -

S. No	Question Description	Yes	Neutral	No	Total	%age
1	They do know their teacher's name	40	0	0	40	100
2	They 're going to school in time	40	0	0	40	100
3	They 're often late from school,	0	0	40	40	100
4	Teachers beat them at their late arrival	0	0	40	40	100
5	They 're acting rudely in school	0	0	40	40	100
6	Teachers are teaching them	40	0	0	40	100
7	They understand what the teachers are teaching.	40	0	0	40	100
8	They 're doing homework in time	40	0	0	40	100
9	Essentials are provided to the school	40	0	0	40	100
10	They use mobile devices in school	0	0	40	40	100
11	Teacher misbehaved them,	0	0	40	40	100
12	Teachers are motivating them	40	0	0	40	100
13	Teachers are checking their homework	40	0	0	40	100

The interviews were very interesting but due to shortage of space, the real position be discussed here. 40 students were asked according to the questionnaire, 100 % student their teacher by name, 100% students are regularly going to school except untoward emergency. 100% students are never late from school so no late no punishment. Their behavior in school is 100 % fine toward their co-mates and teachers. 100 % student showed satisfaction over teaching methodology. 100% students do homework and 100 % is checked by the teachers as well. Most of the essential are provided in schools and 100% prohibition on use of mobile phone by the students in school.

Conclusions, Findings, Suggestions and Recommendations

Conclusions & Findings

Following are the conclusions of the study:

1. The study is been developed in the light of prevailing situation all over Pakistan. All the aspects of education on primary level have been discussed and all the problems that occur in the education system on primary level are mentioned to some extent. Efforts have been made to keep the things clarify. The relation between the student and the teachers has already been given a touch but very minor. Favorable Solutions to the problems on primary level regarding students have been suggested after identification of problems.
2. No doubt that there are many problems that are facing by the students in each class. These problems may be social, financial, domestic, cultural and psychological. The financial problem may be coped with money after income is increased with proper hard work and if luck accompanies, a big amount may be win in lucky draw or a big amount of bond may be win in lottery. The domestic problems may be capped if properly approached. The social problem may also be addressed properly with the support of the society. But the psychological problem cannot be addressed easily as this problem never come alone but this problem brings all other problems along with itself. If on one side it is sickness on the other side it is a big issue that needs a big amount. Again, it needs an experienced expert and psychiatrist to treat the patient. So psychological problems must not be considered lightly, but that must be taken with proper attention.
3. As a nation we all are Muslims and then Pakistani. We must think about the other as well. If anyone the society becomes prey to such like problems then tomorrow it may become a psychological criminal that

will be huge peril to the society. So proper measures may be taken both by the government and the society against the evil in the very bud.

Recommendations

Following are the recommendations to be addressed:

1. It is highly recommended that in future the teachers who are to become on Government pay roll may be initially tested in children psychology.
2. It is also recommended that the newly hired teachers may be trained in children psychology before they are given responsibilities to teach to the children.
3. As it is that Primary schools are the institutions of learning for children so the staff hired for teaching in primary school must have possess positive attitude.
4. It is also suggested that if the female staff is hired for teaching on primary level then the results will be certainly double in success.
5. The psychological problems may be curbed on priority basis.
6. The services of an experienced psychiatrist may be hired only for the primary school students' cause in each district so that the psychological problems to the students may be easily and quickly addressed.

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